

15th ABIS Annual Colloquium

27 OCTOBER 2016 - BRUSSELS

Time for a Change and a New Agenda in Education, Learning & Talent Development

Event Report

Venue - Les Ateliers des Tanneurs

Formerly known as the Wine Palace, the Art nouveau building was a place specialized in the commerce of wine. Completely renovated until 2005, it is now a business centre, Les Ateliers des Tanneurs, that can provide starters with all the space they need to grow and produce the right goods and/or services.

The Ateliers des Tanneurs offers 6,000 m² of totally renovated premises in an attractive and easily accessible district of Brussels, the ideal springboard for new projects in a real hub of economic development. The Ateliers des Tanneurs also has a cafe-restaurant in a truly exceptional setting, conference rooms - the prestigious location to host events and professional meetings (theme-based breakfasts, networking, etc.). It is a project of the CPAS of Brussels and BRUSOC, with the support of Brussels Capital Region and the ERDF.

Context

The past 18 months have been highly significant in terms of the global sustainable development agenda. Acceptance has grown among political leaders, in particular, that urgent collective action is needed to tackle a range of complex, volatile threats to our biosphere and ecology.

As a result, intergovernmental commitments and policies around environmental and social issues – such as the COP21 Paris Agreement, which was just recently reinforced by the Marrakech Conference, UN Sustainable Development Goals and the European Union's Circular Economy (CE) package – have set out clear goals and targets to achieve by 2030.

Huge opportunities await for business transformation and innovation: recent Accenture research suggests a US\$ 4.5 trillion reward for successful CE business models in this timeframe. Yet plenty of other question marks remain, such as:

- Do companies have the right people to grasp these opportunities in a responsible and equitable way?
- Do they understand the implications of digital transformation for their current workforce?
- What will the jobs in a circular, digital future look like?
- What kind of talent, skills and competences will be needed to support these by 2030?

Key stakeholders increasingly accept that these shifts in the global landscape will require a new paradigm in education and talent development, and new sets of organisational & individual capabilities.

This is specifically true with regard to business education, given industry's role as a driver of innovation, jobs, growth and competitiveness, and business schools' role as a connecting hub between the sciences, technology, innovation, management, and more.

As we witnessed throughout the Colloquium, there are pockets of innovation developing in companies and in academia which may help to accelerate the development of dynamic new talent systems. However, the overall debate remains fragmented between public, private and civil sectors. International coalitions for change are very much in their nascent stages. And above all, the scale of today's economic, environmental and social challenges means that we can no longer wait to act.

In this context, the 2016 Colloquium brought together leading voices from industry, academia, youth communities and public policy – as well as those with related interests in global sustainability – to address three main issues, which ultimately frame the entire conference:

1. **Developing** a unified view of shared priorities for change among key stakeholders.
2. **Adapting** and scaling current innovations in business and academia.
3. **Identifying** successful business-academic partnership approaches that deliver measurable impact and change.

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Programme

09:30 – 09:50 Welcome

Alfons Sauquet Rovira (President & Chair of the Board of Directors, ABIS & Global Dean, ESADE)

09:50 – 10:00 Programme Introduction

Joris-Johann Lenssen (Managing Director, ABIS)

10:00 – 11:00 Opening Plenary: The Case for Systemic Change

Speakers: **Dean Van Leeuwen** (Founder, TomorrowToday) **Gary Kildare** (Vice President, Human Resources, IBM Europe) **Maury Peiperl** (Pro Vice Chancellor & Director School of Management, Cranfield University) **Anita Negri** (President of the Executive Board, Oikos International).

Moderator: **Doug Baillie** (Chair of the Strategic Advisory Board, ABIS)

11:00 – 11:30 Coffee Break

11:30 – 12:45 Interactive Sessions: Creating Dynamic Systems of Leadership & Talent Development

BLOCK I: Corporate Innovation Drivers

Session A: The Future Role of Boards

Presenters: **Anthony Carey** (Mazars) & **Annemieke Roodbeek** (Nyenrode Business Universiteit & ABN AMRO Group)

Session B: Building Leadership for Long-Term Business Performance

Presenters: **Patrick Hull** (Unilever) & **Paul Begley** (University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership)

Session C: Anticipating Sustainability Skills & Talent

Presenters: **Doug Baillie** (ABIS) & **Luk van Wassenhove** (INSEAD)

12:45 – 14:00 Networking Lunch

14:00 – 15:15 Interactive Sessions II: Creating Dynamic Systems of Leadership and Talent Development

BLOCK II: Academic Innovation Drivers

Session A: Mainstreaming & The Strategic Case for Change

Presenters: **Petra Molthan Hill** (Nottingham Business School) & **Mirjam Minderman** (Tias School of Business and Society)

Session B: Interdisciplinarity & Breaking Down Walls Between Disciplines

Presenters: **Kosheek Sewchurran** (UCT Graduate School of Business) & **Kaisu Puumalainen** (Lappeenranta University of Technology)

Session C: Faculty Development & Building New Capabilities

Presenters: **Kai Hockerts** (Copenhagen Business School) & **Mollie Painter-Morland** (Nottingham Business School)

15:15 – 15:45 Coffee Break

15:45 – 16:00 Plenary Session: Highlights from Interactive Session Debates

16:00 – 17:00 Plenary Session: Partnerships That Make a Difference

Panellists: **Luke Disney** (Executive Director, INSEAD Centre for Social Innovation) **Sherif Hassane** (Acting Director - Government Affairs - Global Issues, GlaxoSmithKline) **Mollie Painter-Morland** (Professor, Nottingham Business School) **Jan Noterdaeme** (Senior Advisor, CSR Europe & Pact 4 Youth)

Moderator: **Jens Meyer** (Dean of Programs, CEDEP)

17:00 – 17:30 Moving the Agenda Forward

17:30 - 18:30 Drinks Reception

Speakers and Moderators

Doug Baillie

Former Chief HR Officer, Unilever & Chair of the Advisory Board, ABIS

Paul Begley

Programme Director, University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership

Anthony Carey

Partner, Mazars

Luke Disney

Executive Director, INSEAD Centre for Social Innovation

Sherif Hassane

Director Government Affairs -Global Issues, GlaxoSmithKline

Kai Hockerts

Professor, Copenhagen Business School

Patrick Hull

Global Leadership Development Director, Unilever

Gary Kildare

Vice President, Human Resources, IBM Europe

Dean Van Leeuwen

Founder TomorrowToday

Jens Meyer

Dean of Programs, CEDEP

Mirjam Minderman

Policy Adviser/Lecturer, Tias School of Business and Society

Petra Molthan Hill

Principal Lecturer, Nottingham Business School

Anita Negri

President of the Executive Board, Oikos International

Jan Noterdaeme

Senior Advisor, CSR Europe & Coordinator, Pact 4 Youth

Mollie Painter-Morland

Professor, Nottingham Business School

Maury Peiperl

Pro Vice Chancellor & Director School of Management, Cranfield University

Kaisu Puumalainen

Professor, Lappeenranta University of Technology

Annemieke Roobeek

Professor, Nyenrode Business Universiteit & Supervisory Board Member, ABN AMRO Group

Kosheek Sewchurrán

Associate Professor, UCT Graduate School of Business

Luk van Wassenhove

Chaired Professor & Fellow of CEDEP, INSEAD

Session Summaries

The 15th ABIS Annual Colloquium returned our network to its founding mission, and what we hold to be an uncontestable truth: that in order to build a more sustainable world, systemic change is needed in business education and talent development, so that the passion, mindsets, and skills of the next generation of leaders are more effectively harnessed and developed to solve the complex challenges that our planet faces. On the following pages you will find summaries of all Colloquium Sessions providing you with the key discussion points as well as relevant points for our future ABIS agenda which will be considered in our plans for 2017.

Opening Plenary: The Case for Systemic Change

Panellists: Dean Van Leeuwen (TomorrowToday)
Gary Kildare (IBM Europe)
Maury Peiperl (School of Management, Cranfield University)
Anita Negri (Oikos International)
Moderator: Doug Baillie (ABIS Strategic Advisory Board)

This session aimed to connect the business, academic, student and public policy perspectives on why systemic change is so important in our day and age. More importantly, though, it addressed future concerns, uncertainties and questions that will need to be considered as a future of education & talent development agenda moves forward.

The session was kicked off by moderator Doug Baillie, former Chief HR Officer at Unilever and Chair of the ABIS Advisory Board. He outlined the challenges that a volatile, uncertain, complex and ambiguous world brings to today's businesses. These challenges can be attributed to a global rise in population, demand for food, water and energy as well as the related rise in emissions of greenhouse gasses that are currently threatening our common planet.

He noted that many business leaders are now fully aware of these issues and try to tackle them but also use them as an opportunity for future business in the years to come.

As the first panellist, Dean Van Leeuwen - founder of TomorrowToday indicated that millennials have contributed to a change in perspective regarding education, work and personal life. Looking at the world differently - beyond simple profit but aiming to rather contribute to a better tomorrow meaningfully. In this regard, he also stated that the 21st Century will be considered

as the Age of Quests. It will be important for organizations to embed these mindsets into their organizational strategy in order to attract the relevant talent.

Following Mr. Van Leeuwen, Gary Kildare - Vice President of Human Resources at IBM Europe also pointed out that his company experienced these new expectations towards business by millennials. With the knowledge gained at one of the world's leading tech companies, he indicated what impact technology will have on the world in general, as well as on the future of work. He outlined how technology will assist humans in their decision making process but also how it will serve to enhance various aspects of the business value chain in general.

Maury Peiperl - Pro Vice Chancellor & Director at Cranfield School of Management shared with the audience the academic perspective and what it means for business education to adjust to the constant changes in the field. He outlined that vocations are under constant attack by ever more rapidly changing technologies and that the ones responsive to this change will be the ones coming out on top. However, he also sees it as greatly important for businesses to have a long-term strategy that guides them through these somewhat difficult times, which will help them find the right answers to those arising challenges.

As the final panellist, Anita Negri - President of Oikos International shared with the audience the students' perspective and what the aspirations of millennials are regarding sustainability and their future careers. Ms. Negri outlined bad organizational cultures and a leadership crisis as the underpinnings that led in her point of view to an education crisis in which we lack a diffusion of innovation but not innovation in general terms. Speaking for the younger generation, she outlined that people do not just simply want to follow the next position but rather aim to follow their life goals which due to advancements in technologies become more achievable for everyone, regardless of economic or ethnic background.

The following discussion with the audience echoed some of the major remarks pointed out by the panellists, indicating that it is necessary for business to adjust to fast paced changes in technology and that the world of today challenges us to re-think some of the established norms and business practices of past decades. Overall, there was a consensus that organizations need to reflect on the values brought forward by the younger generation not just in order to attract the talent for the future but also to stay competitive in it.

Corporate & Academic Interactive Sessions

It is clear that companies and education institutions will be at the forefront of building the new capabilities, skills and values that will underpin global sustainability progress. Both will however need to undertake a fundamental redesign of traditional approaches to ensure that sustainability is embedded in culture, hearts and minds inside the organisation. Prior to the Colloquium, ABIS has spent a significant amount of time on its [Education Initiative Report](#), mapping out how our academic members are currently developing sustainable, responsible and ethical business education programmes. The feedback we received thus far highlighted the importance to broaden our inquiry into the drivers, obstacles and key success factors behind mainstreaming these issues across educational programmes.

To address this, the following part of the Colloquium featured two blocks of interactive parallel sessions – the first corporate, the second academic. These explored new approaches to creating systems of talent for sustainability, supported by insights from a new ABIS initiative or member innovation. The emphasis throughout is on people-driven debate and a systemic view of the main theme.

BLOCK I: Corporate Innovation Drivers Session A: The Future Role of Boards

Presenters: Anthony Carey (Mazars) & Annemieke Roobeek (Nyenrode Business Universiteit & ABN AMRO Group)

Annemieke Roobeek opened the conversation highlighting how businesses have taken the lead in driving the sustainability agenda forward, while business education seems to be lagging behind. Interviews at Board level with sustainability frontrunners have showed that a mindset shift has taken place about the business case for sustainability and the kind of skills and competences needed to embrace it. This is a very different set of skills than that currently provided by business schools: there is more need for “meta knowledge” (thinking in innovative ways, knowledge about ecosystems and strategies with impact, collaboration etc.) rather than for the best specialized experts. So, the question is around how to rethink the current educational model.

Next, Anthony Carey from Mazars presented some of the insights from the high-level roundtables on the Future Role of Boards in Sustainable Value Creation organized by Mazars and ABIS in September 2016. First of all, there are many strategic challenges and changes that businesses will face in the coming years, including adapting to technological change, responding to climate change, societal challenges, globalization and more, making decision-making processes at board level extremely challenging. In order to adapt to this new reality, boards will need to anticipate and prepare for uncertain futures, to increase their understanding of technology issues and to adapt to the pace of change, to effectively cope with geopolitical turmoil, to diversify their composition and working practices and so forth. Against this backdrop, a key issue seems also to be whether business schools are ready to collaborate with boards and to help address their future needs, in particular whether they are capable of providing grounded, independent, expert guidance on future trends and of educating aware and effective future leaders ready to embrace such challenges.

The discussion that followed focused on:

- The difficulty of reaching a common understanding and agreement on the future trends and integrating them into teaching activities
- The role of millennials in bringing changes in companies and their communities (millennials have a different perspective and they care about their purpose and impact, but how many millennials are in Board rooms?)
- The importance of leadership under pressure and emotional responses
- Need for changes in business governance and at the institutional level
- The management of long term strategies vs short term pressures and the importance of board culture, engaged board members and the company's purpose

TOP CORPORATE PRIORITIES FOR THE ABIS CHANGE AGENDA

- Managing short-term and integrating long-term value creation
- Understand the company's impact on the wider ecosystem
- Mainstreaming sustainability and leadership mindset
- ABIS as the enabler of intercompany living labs among corporate members facilitated by ABIS academic faculty

WHERE BUSINESS SCHOOLS CAN BRING THE MOST VALUE

- Creation of knowledge and understanding of Boards' mechanisms
- Research and promotion of case studies and help businesses to make their business case
- Co-creation with business of new knowledge and learning platforms

BLOCK I: Corporate Innovation Drivers Session B: Building Leadership for Long-Term Business Performance

Presenters: Patrick Hull (Unilever) & Paul Begley (University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership)

This session focused on the prospects of a new industrial age shaped by macro trends, climate challenges and digital transformation that will require companies to be more agile, resilient and entrepreneurial than ever. Patrick Hull from Unilever showcased how the company in line with its Sustainable Living Plan is trying to tackle these prominent issues. Whilst Unilever has been very capable to adjust its supply chain accordingly, a main challenge still arises in the way they hire and train future talent to be able to systematically analyze and cope with these challenges. In relation to this, Unilever also noticed that through being very vocal about sustainability issues, including their CEO Paul Polman, the organization became very attractive for recent graduates. However, a general issue still remains with the development of KPIs for managers as well as creating the right mindset to tackle current & future challenges of the organization. Paul Begley from the University of Cambridge Institute further underlined this difficulty for Sustainability Leadership, stating that it is necessary for management to ask the right questions in order to achieve results that one can measure within the organization.

Participants then focused on how the challenges affect their organizations. Stating for example that the banking sector is faced with dramatic changes regarding their business model, with current leaders having to shift their focus & skills to being able to orchestrate their teams and provide them with a clear and engaging purpose. Most organizations present seemed to struggle with defining or aligning their KPIs with a changing business model, as well as trying to measure process towards long-term goals on an annual or even quarterly basis. Towards the end of the discussion, it seemed to be clear that these challenges as well as a clear integration of systems thinking into overall strategy and day-to-day tasks seem the core challenges for business today.

TOP CORPORATE PRIORITIES FOR THE ABIS CHANGE AGENDA

- Create space for collaboration more than competition. Set the limits between Cooperation and Competition
- Co-ompetition
- Identify and set purpose – Leaders & Employees
- Bring on board SME and leaders entrepreneurs
- ABIS should create a new vocabulary for the leaders of the future
- Make ABIS a place to make beautiful questions.
- ABIS should use the SDGs to set a new leadership agenda
- ABIS should create a virtual market place online where to share teaching cases, workshop business schools and corporation have developed around teaching collaboration to leaders

BLOCK I: Corporate Innovation Drivers

Session C: Anticipating Future Skills and Leadership for Sustainable Business

Presenters: Doug Baillie (ABIS Strategic Advisory Board) & Luk Van Wassenhove (INSEAD)

This session focused on the challenges companies and business schools face in trying to anticipate, define and develop the talent which business will need to survive and thrive in an era of unprecedented volatility and systemic pressures. Doug Baillie framed sustainability as a journey for companies that is framed by dual contexts: the future world in which we wish to live, and the current trends shaping the business environment. For Unilever, four drivers guide the company's trajectory: power shifts to the East and South; digitalization and related discontinuities; lifestyle changes and urbanization; and the end of the age of abundance. The new realities mean that large companies like Unilever have to rethink and reinvent themselves: by sharing power, by co-creating solutions, and by engaging in effective partnerships. Moreover, business model innovation increasingly needs to deliver enhanced livelihoods and social impact for huge numbers of citizens and consumers. The major challenge is building this mindset into the DNA of the firm – both "hardware" and "software", underpinned by qualities like resilience, adaptability and empathy. Luk Van Wassenhove highlighted the urgent need for collaboration to respond to global sustainability challenges – but noted that the bureaucratic nature of organisations obstructs this, leading also to a significant loss of commitment within the workforce towards their employers. The responsibility and accountability for leadership deficits are debated in a polarized manner (in particular companies vs. business schools), which is counter-productive to any kind of progress. The principles of strategic agility point to the kind of talent needed to reinvigorate and lead more sustainable organisations: people who are capable of harnessing the power of networks, of fluidity, of purpose, and of diversity. Finding this kind of talent is not the issue; managing it well is the critical gap to be bridged, and convening proper dialogue about how organisations can reform their structures and cultures to allow this talent to blossom. There is no "silver bullet" on how to do this – they have to commit to experimentation and be willing to fail and learn from the experience.

TOP PRIORITIES FOR THE ABIS CHANGE AGENDA

- "Lay out the road, don't fill in the cracks" – and ensure that the millennial voice is brought into the heart of the debate
- Identify and define the disconnects in the current education system
- Build cross-sector agreement @ talent qualities for strategic agility, and what they mean in practice
- Survival skills for a VUCA world need to be embedded in everything that is taught – break down the big ideas and see where they fit
- Don't forget organisational context – what changes are needed to allow talent to flourish?

BLOCK II: Academic Innovation Drivers

Session A: Mainstreaming & The Strategic Case for Change

Presenters: Petra Molthan Hill (Nottingham Business School) & Mirjam Minderman (Tias School of Business and Society)

Nowadays, transformational leadership skills are incredibly sought after. Companies and other organizations are searching for leaders capable of combining market-leading financial performance with sustainability leadership. At the same time, the context organizations are operating in is going through massive changes:

- technological progress creates new economic realities that revolutionize innovation, production and distribution; structural demographic changes like aging, immigration, urbanization will have tremendous impact on business and society;
- rising ecological challenges prompt both industry and the public to put increasing value on conducting business in ecologically sustainable ways;
- uncontrolled market capitalism, irresponsible risk taking, narrow self-interest/fraud etc. triggered a demand for moral re-grounding and institutional reforms.

Management education has a significant role to play in empowering people and organizations to operate and thrive in such context: integrating sustainability across curricula is one of the levers business schools and universities can do so. The presenters shared key success factors behind formulating a strategic case for change, securing the buy-in of key stakeholders, and ultimately implementing the organizational transformation process required for mainstreaming sustainability. Both presenters agreed on a holistic, integrative view where business schools need to co-operate with businesses, public entities and (civil) society in order to solve social and environmental issues and to create (shared) value. They identified four main challenges and solutions in implementing such approach:

1. Definition of sustainability. The lack of a clear and shared understanding of sustainability is often a first obstacle. The presenters provided two ways to overcome it: focusing on concrete challenges (e.g. food) rather than on abstract concepts can be very helpful and creating a reference framework (e.g. TIAS Business and Society Competency Framework)
2. Engagement of colleagues. Colleagues often seem not interested to integrate sustainability in their teaching due to lack of time and/or knowledge, apparent irrelevance of the issue for their area of activities, and the difficul-

ties to change existing curricula etc. A powerful way to overcome such resistance is to offer instead of asking, by making concepts more concrete, making what already exists more visible, providing examples and inspiration and stimulating (cross-disciplinary) collaboration. This could be done by developing and sharing ready to use resources e.g. NBS has developed an online ESD Future Thinking Learning Room with resources for each of the UN Sustainable Development Goals as well as for each of the disciplines within the Business School.

3. Engagement of students. Besides embedding sustainability-related issues in the teaching content, it is important to engage students by inviting relevant guest speakers, organizing student consulting projects and making it fun! For instance, NBS, has developed a Sustainability in Practice Certificate (compulsory within both Masters and Undergraduate modules) as well as a FT MScBA Student Consultancy through which students are encouraged to explore the meanings of sustainability.
4. Further integration. There is a need to balance top-down vs bottom-up approaches and to include external stakeholders (e.g. Advisory Board, LABs). The role of accreditations in mainstreaming sustainability is largely unexplored and could serve as a powerful incentive, also given the tensions in current sustainability rankings. It is clear that it is a process that does not happen overnight, but it bears the first fruits whenever students and colleagues start asking questions.

TOP ACADEMIC PRIORITIES FOR THE ABIS CHANGE AGENDA

- Starting from the problem e.g. food (concrete sustainability-related issues)
- Research as a binding factor to engage in sustainability issues and engage external stakeholders
- Link to faculty development and innovations in education/pedagogy
- Start from the context/purpose of students, faculty and business

WHERE BUSINESS CAN BRING THE MOST VALUE

- Driver for change: demanding transformation in programs and skills
- Engaging in research
- Providing resources

BLOCK II: Academic Innovation Drivers

Session B: Interdisciplinarity & Breaking Down Walls Between Disciplines

Presenters: Kosheek Sewchurran (UCT Graduate School of Business) & Kaisu Puumalainen (Lappeenranta University of Technology)

Business schools are ideally positioned to collaborate with the 'hard' and 'soft' sciences to create new education frameworks and content that develop sustainability skills and competences. In this session, Kaisu Puumalainen introduced the LUT Trailblazer strategy, which aims to tackle sustainability issues through a set of interdisciplinary research platforms at LUT. These platforms link different schools and faculties together to conduct research with an interdisciplinary perspective. So far, this platform yielded mixed results in linking various disciplines with some seeming to be easier to link than other. Another critical issue that LUT identified is the issue of young scholars possibly risking their careers, with leading journals being mainly publishing articles solely related to one particular discipline. Thus, being stuck in silo-thinking and possibly not valuing interdisciplinary research enough.

Following the presentation from LUT, Kosheek Sewchurran presented what interdisciplinarity means for executive management education. He outlined the need for managers being able to find the right variables such as consumer behavior, trends, regulatory uncertainties, shifting competition, new technologies etc. that affect the success of their business. To do so, managers need to be able to focus on those variables through a set of different lenses which are different from those developed in mainstream business school programmes.

After the two presentations, the discussion turned onto the necessity to have interdisciplinarity and systems thinking both in academic research and the development of future business leaders. These insights are reflected in the suggestions for the ABIS network to further enhance interdisciplinarity among the different sectors.

TOP ACADEMIC PRIORITIES FOR THE ABIS CHANGE AGENDA

- Bring more reality into the classroom
- Get reality accepted at the academic level
- Accepting complexity
- Focus on institutional logic
- Create an interdisciplinary journal

WHERE BUSINESS CAN BRING THE MOST VALUE

- Talk about / offer failed & successful cases
- Emphasize systems thinking as a core capability (re-launch)
- Talk about integrative thinking & business models
- Sanity checks

BLOCK II: Academic Innovation Drivers Session C: Faculty Development & Building New Capabilities

Presenters: Kai Hockerts (Copenhagen Business School) & Mollie Painter-Morland (Nottingham Business School & ABIS)

This session focused on the ways to deepen sustainability commitments and pedagogic skills across an entire faculty and to increase the materiality of sustainability teaching and research to overall career prospects. Kai Hockerts from Copenhagen Business School presented the results from a survey among PRME Signatories on Faculty Development for Responsible Management Education. Furthermore, he explained the time scale and process for the development of the survey. Mollie Painter-Morland from Nottingham Business School further underlined why sustainability educators have a vital role to play in driving forward a new agenda and the challenges faced by these educators in career development. Furthermore, she showcased her experiences around faculty development. Namely, the methodology to incentivize faculty, the issues around the lack of a common language and how overcome it, highlighting the importance of collecting syllabi.

Participants then focused on how what where the priorities of faculty development and how to best address them. Furthermore, how business could potentially support faculty development. The participants then had a discussion around specific challenges that affect their own organizations. Stating for example organizational limitations, either human or financial, access to resources to good case studies and insights to concerns of businesses and the barriers to change. The participants also shared the formal and informal activities in place that are enhancing faculty knowledge and practice. Towards the end of the discussion, the participants seemed to agree that pressure on faculty doesn't allow to make the necessary investments or changes in teaching and that there is a need to know how motivate faculty letting them own the process.

TOP ACADEMIC PRIORITIES FOR THE ABIS CHANGE AGENDA

- Creation of an ABIS-PRME certificated course
- ABIS to hold a communication campaign on resources available
- Creation of shared terms vocabulary
- Mainstreaming sustainability mentorship

WHERE BUSINESS CAN BRING THE MOST VALUE

- Employer voice
- Top quotes from corporates
- Bring examples into the classroom
- Corporate placements with feedback into courses

Plenary Session: Partnerships That Make a Difference

Panellists: Luke Disney (INSEAD Centre for Social Innovation)
Sherif Hassane (GlaxoSmithKline)

Mollie Painter-Morland (Nottingham Business School & ABIS)

Jan Noterdaeme (CSR Europe & Pact 4 Youth)

Moderator: Jens Meyer (CEDEP & ABIS)

Partnerships can be the solution to many problems, but can also be a source of the same. The session was designed to examine some of the empirical aspects of successful partnerships. Participants gained insights from real-live experiences of leading ABIS members and strategic partners on a range of collaboration models: from the North Star Alliance on a cross-African collaboration, from GlaxoSmithKline on international capacity-building partnerships including developing markets; from Nottingham Business School on co-creating leadership programmes in Africa, and from CSR Europe on building business-education partnerships in a high-level policy context.

The plenary started off with Luke Disney introducing the Northstar Alliance's way to tackle HIV problems in the truck industry in Africa. The way this business model managed to work was through partnerships with different stakeholders trying to jointly tackle the issue. Besides failures in business model, profitability and other issues, Disney outlined that the one critical thing that made the project a success over several years was indeed the complex partnership between the stakeholders as well as the identification with the project as such and the common goal that the group worked on through collaboration, which in turn resulted in a high level of resilience in the partnerships.

Afterwards, Sherif Hassane tackled the importance of a partnership model to understand the problems that GSK is trying to solve in Sub-Saharan African countries. One of the main issues that GSK tries to solve is the lack of good governance and the problem of corruption in those countries. Through this ABIS Africa Initiative which is led by GSK together with other ABIS corporate and academic partners, the partnership aims to educate business professionals around these important issues. The community of practitioners that formed through this initiative helped to create peer-to-peer partnerships that educate its participants through collaboration. For GSK, the main lessons learned from it were that they have to be demand-led, bottom up, problem-based, and interdisciplinary.

Following Shaerif Hassane, Mollie Painter-Morland further built on the ABIS leadership initiative in Africa, outlining the governing challenges that it aims to tackle cross-sectorally. To her, one of the key points that led to its success were the clear business-driven problems underlying the project, which were

brought in by the three companies (GSK, IBM & Unilever). One of the outcomes from the official launch of this initiative was that participants greatly valued the cross-sectorial engagement. Hence, not necessarily needing tailored approaches for every participant and his or her sector of work.

As final panellist, Jan Noterdaeme brought the audience back to the origins of ABIS, outlining the fundamental reasons why a partnership model like ABIS is so important in order to tackle complex issues. He then introduced the European Pact 4 Youth project, which tries to break the silos of education, policy and business in order to tackle the large issue of youth unemployment in Europe. In light of this project, he advocated the need for smart partnerships between the mentioned stakeholders already in pre-university education to tackle Europe's unemployment issues sustainably for the long-term. Building on this, he outlined different ways to create business-educational partnerships, which may be achieved through companies being present at schools, apprenticeships, or other possibilities of to gain work experience for students early on.

After the four presentations, the audience was asked to provide feedback or their insights on what is necessary to form successful partnerships. The key points that came out from this discussion were that it seems to be very important to embrace failure, especially for young business leaders, when taking on complex challenges. It also came through that there needs to be a general reform in the way teaching is done, which embraces new technologies creating new forms of collaboration, interaction and learning for students. As a final point, it was noted that in order to bring various initiatives forward and to create meaningful impact with them it is of absolute importance that they to some degree follow the same mission or purpose, in order for them not to be seen as isolated lighthouse projects.

About ABIS

ABIS - The Academy of Business in Society is a global network of over 100 companies, academic and affiliated institutions whose expertise, commitment and resources are leveraged to invest in a more sustainable future for business in society.

ABIS (formerly known as EABIS) was founded in 2002 in partnership with IBM, Microsoft, Johnson & Johnson, Unilever and Shell and with the support of Europe's leading Business Schools (INSEAD, IMD, London Business School, ESA-DE, IESE, Copenhagen Business School, Warwick Business School, Vlerick Business School, Ashridge Business School, Cranfield, SDA Bocconi School of Management).

The creation of ABIS was driven by a shared belief that challenges linked to globalisation and sustainable development required new management skills, mindsets & capabilities. The ABIS network aims to build new educational frameworks through the creation of new knowledge and its application in various member initiatives.

What We Do

The ABIS business-academic partnership model is based on three pillars of engagement which support the culture, mindsets, processes and skills to create organisational transformation:

THINK - Fostering thought leadership through collaborative dialogue and deep reflection

SHARE - Facilitating knowledge development, translation and shared learning

INTEGRATE - Applying knowledge in the organizational context to drive innovation and change

These are translated into a wide range of platforms, projects and events, of varying scope and size – from €5 million industry-focused research grants to international thought leadership conferences and case study development.

Contact

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